

OPTIMIZING PRECONCEPTION PREPARATION FOR WOMEN WHO BECOME PREGNANT DUE TO CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS

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Abstract: Chronic endometritis is one of the most common inflammatory diseases of the female reproductive system. Timely treatment of the disease is insurance against serious complications, including oncology and infertility.

The endometrium is the lining of the uterus. Acute endometritis develops when it becomes inflamed as a result of pathogenic bacteria. The chronic stage of the disease usually occurs as a result of lack of treatment.

Key words: Reproductive health, Chronic endometritis, Features of acute endometritis.

Women of reproductive age are at risk they account for about 97% of all detected cases of the disease. Many women later cannot conceive a child due to long-term inflammation in the uterus, and about 30% of patients with endometritis become infertile.

Women who have morphological and functional changes in the uterus as a result of endometritis often cannot get pregnant even as a result of IVF. This is due to the inability of tissues to perceive hormonal stimulation and maintain natural cyclical changes.

Features of acute endometritis

The acute stage of the disease develops like any infection - quickly, with a rapid increase in symptoms. Tissue inflammation develops immediately after infectious agents enter the endometrium. The situation worsens and the localization of the pain syndrome indicates a gynecological disease. Some signs indicate acute inflammation:

- An increase in body temperature and shivering;
- Vaginal discharge with blood;
- Spasms in the lower abdomen and lumbar region;
- Heavy menstruation.

The disease is characterized by symptoms of general weakness - weakness, loss of appetite, drowsiness, increased sweating. The acute form becomes chronic in about a month. If you consult a doctor in time, the acute process can be treated within a week and a half.

Causes of chronic endometritis

The chronicity of the disease occurs due to the timely treatment of the acute stage of the disease or premature completion of therapy. The penetration of pathogenic microflora into the uterine cavity occurs through the ascending route - from the vagina. Precipitating factors for the development of inflammation:

1. Childbirth, abortion, gynecological operations;
2. Diagnostic manipulations;
3. Menstruation, intercourse during menstruation;
4. Infectious processes developing in other organs;

5. Weakening of the immune system.

Symptoms of chronic endometritis

When examined by a gynecologist for this disease, the expansion of the uterus and pain during palpation are detected. The patient also has the following symptoms:

1. Pain in the suprapubic region;
2. Heaviness and cramping in the lower abdomen;
3. Lumbar pain syndrome;
4. Brown vaginal discharge.

The inflammatory process occurs with periodic exacerbations and remissions. But even during the clinical course, there are menstrual disorders, pain in the lower abdomen and mucous discharge. During the chronic process, changes in the structure of the endometrium occur. The functionality of the inner uterine layer can be restored only with systemic therapy.

Diagnosis of chronic endometritis

In the chronic stage of the disease, the symptoms are smooth, so it becomes difficult to diagnose. But the gynecologist's experience, modern hardware technologies and the laboratory.

Diagnosis of the disease is carried out in several stages:

Examination by a gynecologist to identify the provoking factors of pathology and analyze complaints.

Study of medical history, information about abortions, operations, methods of contraception.

Examination of the size of the uterus, appendages, detection of flow, pain when pressed with fingers.

The use of information diagnostic methods includes general and biochemical blood tests, general urinalysis, pelvic ultrasound, diagnostic curettage for bacteriological and pathomorphological examination. A smear and secretion analysis is carried out, the purpose of which is to determine the type of pathogen.

If the diagnosis is suspected, computer tomography, MRI, hysteroscopy are used and medical advice is prescribed. After the diagnosis, a complex treatment scheme is prescribed.

Treatment of chronic endometritis

The goal of treatment is to restore the endometrial tissue and the woman's ability to conceive. Antibiotics are needed to eliminate the infectious process caused by the introduction of bacterial pathogens. Products with a wide range of effects are used. Complex therapy of the disease includes the use of anti-inflammatory, antifungal agents and antispasmodics aimed at eliminating symptoms.

Medicines are prescribed only by a doctor, self-medication is unacceptable, because wrongly selected medicines cause complications. Even common remedies, such as antifungal suppositories, should be used after consulting a doctor. The specialist's prescriptions are based on the test results, so they bring the greatest benefit and speed up recovery.

Physiotherapy is the last measure in treatment. Physiotherapy procedures used are aimed at accelerating tissue regeneration and strengthening the immune system:

Magnetotherapy - eliminates swelling, inflammation, restores blood microcirculation and helps to activate the immune system.

UHF therapy - used during exacerbations, is designed to increase blood flow, which helps to saturate tissues with useful substances for regeneration.

Electrophoresis is performed using drugs. Anti-inflammatory, absorbable and pain-relieving drugs are used.

Ultrasound - ensures the transport of nutrients to damaged tissues and helps their recovery.

All stages of treatment must be completed completely, because untreated endometritis causes complications that affect a woman's health and quality of life.

For women planning pregnancy, endometritis should be fully treated, as an unhealthy lining of the uterus can lead to miscarriage. If the disease is the result of an infection acquired during childbirth or cesarean section, then the treatment should be as gentle as possible. You can only take medications that do not affect the composition of breast milk.

Antibacterial therapy should not last more than 10 days, because antibiotics affect the intestinal and vaginal microflora. Dysbiosis and candidiasis can develop as a result of an incorrect treatment scheme.

Competent therapy includes a combination of anti-inflammatory, antibacterial and antispasmodic drugs. Complex methods of exposure are also used - oral administration of drugs, vaginal suppositories, injections.

Preventive measures should not be neglected, because the disease may recur. To avoid this, you should carefully observe the hygiene of the genital organs, use contraceptives to avoid abortion, and avoid casual sex.

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